

Blockvote – Block Chain Based Voting System

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Abstract—**BLOCKVOTE** is the new voting system utilizing blockchain technology to upgrade the nature of elections conducted by us. Traditional voting is usually suspected with fraud, lack of transparency, and inefficiency. Blockchain's nature of decentralization and high security makes it opportune for making voting more secure, transparent, and efficient. With **BLOCKVOTE**, blockchain technology displays real potential in overing even voting systems. A safe, transparent and efficient alternative to the traditional methods. This project looks to lay a foundation for future research and development regarding blockchain-based voting systems toward improving democratic systems globally. In this paper, we present **BLOCKVOTE**, its architecture, its security features, and the ease with which one can use it. The system employs smart contracts to automate and secure the vote. The process ensures that every vote is recorded and can never be changed. A strong verification of identity process handles the authentication of the voter in that only eligible voters can vote. A decentralized ledger used in **BLOCKVOTE** ensures that each vote forms a verifiable audit trail, viewable by the public, therefore encouraging trust in the election process. It addresses also questions of scalability and privacy to make sure that it can amicably handle big elections without the disclosure of voters' identity.

Keywords—Blockchain, Architecture, Authentication.

I. INTRODUCTION

The modern democracies base their processes on the will of the people through voting. Today, most countries rely on the legacy ballot system that has to depend on centralized control with a trusted party for carrying out the voting process and the recording and counting of the vote ballots by the trusted third party. That has, however brought in the possibility of corruption and manipulation of votes. A ballot system, an electronic voting, or e-voting, system has been proposed and implemented in limited scenarios, due to its promising capabilities of reducing costs and decreasing manual intervention. However, e-voting systems have not been implemented on a large-scale due to concerns regarding security, transparency, distributed authority, data integrity, privacy and compliance requirements.

An election, which takes place in the form of voting, is a process that involves members competing with each other. This forces us to have a system that is highly secure and cannot be tampered with by the third party that conducts the elections or the voters participating in the elections. Such a process cannot be secured using just the cryptography process alone. If the secret key used in the cryptography, the process is determined or altered by the party conducting the elections, the whole system fails and is not secure.

In such an environment, it becomes essential to follow policies such as the distributed ledger. Blockchain being a technology that makes use of distributed ledgers, can be perfectly applied to this process. The blockchain network can either be a permission-less network like Bitcoin or Ethereum where anybody is allowed to interact with the network, or a permissioned network like Hyperledger Fabric, Hyperledger Sawtooth or exonum where only known members are allowed to interact with the network. Another important issue to be addressed is the anonymity of the voter. Due to the rise in research and development in the field of big data analytics, this data is vulnerable to uncovering and manipulation. Remedied by incorporating techniques such as one-time ring signatures and homomorphic encryption.

The ideology of designing and implementing an e-voting system using blockchain overcomes the majority of drawbacks of standard e-voting systems and provides encouraging research initiatives. The fundamentally decentralized nature of blockchain conceptualizes the technology as a secure third party. In this manner, an e-voting system implemented using the blockchain technology can be trusted to add only valid and verified voting blocks to the blockchain network. Moreover, Any form of hacking or attempted alteration of the blocks in the blockchain is considered a breach of the blockchain network's consensus principles and is not permitted by the blockchain network. Thus, an e-voting system based on blockchain is convenient, automated, transparent, secure and uncoerced.

II. RELATED RESEARCH

A. The Blockchain Technology

Blockchain is so called because it is a chain of blocks, which means that it is a chain of interconnected nodes, all of whom have their version of the distributed ledger that holds the history of all transactions that occur. The data is processed and entered into a block in a process known as mining. Every block contains a hash of the previous block and thus it forms a chain of blocks, with the first block known as the Genesis block. Therefore, it is a linked list type of structure. Blockchain has several ledgers where data can be only appended but not deleted or altered. As a result, it is unalterable. Blockchain can be either public, where anyone can read or write data on the blockchain, or private (permissioned), in which case only a few restricted individuals can read or write data.

B. Electronic Voting Machine (EVM)

Electronic Voting Machines are the replacement of ballot boxes in the election process. EVMs first time used in a general election in Kerala in May of 1982. However, since there was no particular legislation that made their use mandatory, the Supreme Court declared that election null and

void. In 1999, the electronic voting machines or EVMs were used for the first time in a general election (statewide) to the Goa assembly inspired with the fact that EVMs are used in all by-elections and state elections of 2003, the election commission resolved to employ EVMs in all 543 Parliamentary Constituencies in the country for the Lok Sabha elections in 2004. EVM, which comprises of 2 parts was ushered in as a solution to the challenges inherent in ballot paper systems:

1. Control Unit: It gather and tabulate the votes, that are used by the polling operators.
2. Ballot Unit: It is installed at the polling place and is used by the voters to exercise their franchise.

Votes are accurately captured on EVMs, and all issues associated with them, such as calculation, measurement, accuracy, immediate declaration of effects, and system robustness have become clearly obvious. But the major issue is that of authentic verification-the voting individual may not be a legitimate person actually present. The other issues are the ruling political party operating from booths, voting for elderly, and fraudulent voting-all seem possible.

III. METHODOLOGY

Ensuring complete anonymity of the election process, by eliminating all correlation between voters and votes without the additional storage and computational overhead of separate blockchains for voter information and the vote information is required.

Various existing designs for blockchain based e-voting systems incorporate the ability of the election administration to query the blockchain during the election process in order to check if the voter ID of the current voting block already exists in the blockchain, which introduces the possibility of inequitable misuse by accessing count of votes information during the election.

IV. ARCHITECTURE

We will introduce our proposed methodology with user-friendly interface, and also a practical implementation of the blockchain concept in the backend to the safety of the election process, toward making the voting easier and more efficient processing. The following steps are mentioning the system:

- Step 1: Whenever the candidate used to open the website, he would be re-directed to the log-in page, where he would put in his credentials and proceed to the main page of the website.
- Step 2: All information concerning the elections conducted along with the candidates and their respective progress, the user was briefed on the dashboard.
- Step 3: The voter would himself get registered through the website for the current elections with all the required information and with a password. Once the process gets completed, then the voter will get registered along with generating a unique number of voters for that particular user.
- Step 4: A particular transaction which illustrates Candidate will be the appending the first transaction to a block. It shall be regarded as a starting point and not considered a vote. There will be verification of user details with the government database in the step above. This is the final verifying step. In case it is not available, then verification shall not take place.
- Step 5: Once all the process of registration is done, the user would go the voting website where he would be able to vote by putting his username that would be the unique voter id

generated and the password that the voter has set, after putting all the details the voter would be guided to the vote casting section.

Step 6: In the voting section, the voter will get the information about the candidates chosen currently for election, vote casting prompt would be used by the voter for voting his preferable candidate and after that the process of voting would be completed. The candidate would not change his vote and manipulate data when the vote is casted.

Step 7: Following the voting procedure, votes would be encrypted using the SHA-1 one-way hash algorithm to lock them against outside interference. This also eliminates any vote tampering with the user's votes.

The block will then be time-stamped and forwarded to the next checkpoint. This will serve as a pointer to the most recent update to the blockchain upon receipt of the encrypted version of the user's block. At this timestamp the next checkpoint in the process will be validated. This step ensures that this block is connected to the node of the next checkpoint and entered to the blockchain. Accordingly, the data would be added in the blockchain.

Fig: System Architecture

a) Voting protocol diagram b) Blockchain evoting system

Fig: Simple Architecture of Blockchain voting

concluded that both systems have their benefits, but further refinement of the blockchain technology is needed to develop clear, secure, and trustful voting mechanisms.

Fig: Admin Login

V. EVALUATION

The Merkle Tree approach used in this present research on blockchain-based voting systems was found to outshine traditional database structures, primarily in terms of security and tamper resistance. A Merkle Tree is a cryptographic tool that gives integrity into data by aggregation through hashes and is apropos to the transparency and auditability mechanisms inherent in voting systems, though simple; it proved to be very efficient when securing voter data.

Although traditional databases work very well most of the time, their effectiveness is less in terms of immutability and trustworthiness of the data stored. Blockchain-based solutions, though slower, provide decentralised security and also make tampering nearly impossible because every transaction is tracked. Each system has its benefits: the scalability of traditional databases is combined with the security and transparency of blockchain. The greater the complexity of the blockchain, the more it promises a promising alternative to existent systems, especially when safety and trust are most essential in the situation. Our research highlights blockchain, mainly Merkle Trees, as a very effective tool for secure, reliable voting systems meant to increase public confidence in their elections.

VI. RESULT

In our voting systems comparison work, we used traditional databases as well as blockchain-based systems using Merkle Trees. In a surprising manner, the blockchain-based approach proved to outperform the traditional database system, especially with regards to security and tamper resistance.

Merkle Trees ensured good vote integrity owing to the mechanism tracking every transaction, while the traditional database system seemed more appropriate in terms of high speed and scalability.

While more expensive than the traditional databases, blockchain came out as the even more reliable solution in securing votes. Given all the considerations above, it is

Fig: Admin Details

Fig: Add Schedule

Fig: Add Voter

Fig: User List

Fig: Token Generation

Fig: Candidate Registration

Fig: Voter Login

Fig: Candidate Details

Fig: Vote Cast

Fig: Voter Registration

Fig: Vote Success

Fig: Vote Validation

Fig: Result

Fig: Vote Recasting

VII. CONCLUSION

To solve the issue of traditional voting systems, e-voting systems using blockchain is a promising research project. Blockchain systems maintain security, reliability, decentralized storage and anonymity. Through designing and implementing e-voting systems using blockchain, public and individual verifiability, dependability, reliability, consistency, auditability, anonymity, transparency, scalability, eligibility, authentication and fairness can be achieved through the principles of consensus, cryptography, digital signatures and various blockchain mechanisms. The Hyperledger saw tooth framework, because of support for parallel processing of transactions, is the ideal implementation in terms of making the e-voting system faster, lighter, and scalable. Future areas of research can be extended for frameworks Like Hyperledger Sawtooth in the direction of designing and implementing realistic, robust and practical e-voting systems which can be employed to large and broad and voting scenarios. This study presented not only encourages the exploration of such blockchain technology in practical voting processes but also demonstrates the plausibility of applying blockchain to develop secure and reliable systems in many areas like finance, supply chain, trade, and so on.

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